

Scale up of light-driven hydrogen evolution to the liter scale using thiomolybdate-modified photocatalysts in a mass transport intensified loop photoreactor – Scaling synthetic procedures and operational conditions as key for scalability

(Supporting Information)

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1. Detailed Information on used Photoreactors

1.1 Modular Photoreactor

For the HER experiments, two setups consisting of the modular photoreactor, a magnetic stirrer, and a laboratory power supply were arranged side by side, as shown in Figure 1. This

Figure 1. Experimental setup for HER experiments in the modular photoreactor. Two setups were arranged, each consisting of a modular photoreactor, a magnetic stirrer, and a laboratory power supply (Korad KA3005P).

configuration enabled parallel experiments to be conducted in the modular photoreactor. All sample preparation was carried out in a glovebox under argon atmosphere. For HER experiments 8 (5 mL GC vials) were filled with 2 mL of the respective reaction solution and equipped with PTFE coated magnetic stirring bars (3x6 mm). The vials were capped using screwcaps and positioned in the modular photoreactor placed on a magnetic stirrer. For HER experiments with stirring, the stirring speed was set to 600 rpm. The GC vial were placed within the modular photoreactor in the 8-vial (circular diameter = 46.4 mm) sample holder at a distance vertical distance of 7 cm from the irradiation module and aligned with an additional 8-vial alignment ring fixed at a vertical position of 6 cm. Experiments were conducted using the 90x90x100 mm modular photoreactor corpus printed from white PLA (Raise 3D premium)^[1]. Hydrogen production was monitored by serial probing of the vial headspace using gas chromatography (Bruker Scion SQ, TCD detector). To ensure similar irradiation conditions for each irradiation cycle, the probed vial was replaced by a dummy vial filled with 2 mL saturated aqueous methyl orange solution and placed at the original position within the modular photoreactor. Irradiation was performed using two LED types UV 365 nm and blue 455 nm (for detailed information see Table 4). The reaction chamber was ventilated using a fan ($26 \text{ L} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) to avoid heating of the reaction chamber.

1.2 0.5 L Stirred Looping Photoreactor (SLPR)

Figure 2: Picture of 0.5 L SLPR setup with the cooling jacket (1), LED heatsinks (2) with connection to the power supply (3), reactor opening for the magnetic stirrer coupling (4), opening for reagent addition (5), line to the GC (6), mass flow controller (7), and the cooling water inlet (8-1) and outlet (8-2) (left), detailed setup flow chart (right) R-1: Stirred Loop Photoreactor, MFC-1: mass flow controller, CV-1: check valve (gas), V-1: two-way valve (liquid exhaust), M: overhead stirrer, LED-1: LED module, PS-1: power supply, HE-1: cryostat, B-1: gas scrubber, GC: gas chromatograph.

The stirred looping photoreactor (SLPR) proposed by Li et al.^[2] was modified with a DURAN borosilicate glass cooling jacket (d = 90 mm, l = 160 mm, GGM Pfau^[3]: SCHOTT D09025). All used setup components are listed in Table 2. The setup is shown in Figure 2. Two heatsinks (ATS-EXL75-300-R0, Advanced Thermal Solutions INC.), each equipped with three LEDs, were mounted around the cooling jacket (1,2) and connected to power supplies (Korad KA3005P) (3). The reactor's top opening (4) accommodated the magnetic stirrer coupling (P-MRK, BOLA) driving the stirrer shaft. Through a second opening (5), the reaction mixture was added. A third opening (6) connected the tube transporting the generated hydrogen, carried by argon, through a molecular sieve (CAS: 308080-99-1, Thermo Scientific) to the GC (Thermo Scientific Trace 1310, detector: TCD) for continuous sampling every 11 min. Pure argon was fed into the reactor through a lower inlet, with flow controlled by a mass flow controller (F-201CV-200-RGD-11-E, Bronkhorst) (7). The MFC was protected from liquid pushback from the SLPR by a check valve (SS-2C-1 Swagelok). Cooling water entered through line 8-1 and exits via 8-2.

1.3 3 L Stirred Looping Photoreactor (SLPR)

Figure 3: Depiction of 3 L SLPR parts (left), detailed information on reactor dimensions (right).

The 3 L stirred looping photoreactor (SLPR) depicts a scaled version (scaling factor 6) of the 0.5 L SLPR proposed by Li et al.^[2] Figure 3 depicts the assembled 3 L SLPR, reactor components and dimensions. All SLPR glass components were purchased from GGM Pfaudler^[3] and were manufactured from borosilicate listed in Table 1. The SLPR consisted of:

- a top part consisting of a DN 100 rounded cover (1), equipped with a NS 29/32 connector (2) and two GL 18 screw connectors (3)
- a middle part consisting of a removable draft tube (5), a reactor tube (6) equipped with two pipe section connectors (4) and a cooling jacket (7)
- a bottom part consisting of a GL 18 screw connector (2)

The draft tube was fixed from the top and bottom in the middle part using two 3D printed draft tube holders (8) and two connecting rods with M4 threads (9) using M4 screws. Bottom and top part were connected to the middle part using two quick release fasteners (10). The reactor parts were sealed using two silicon O-rings (11) placed in the grooves of the middle

part. The SLPR was equipped with a stirring rod (12) with four 3D printed stirrers (13) mounted equally spaced along the draft tube and a bottom stirrer (14) mounted below the lower draft tube holder in the bottom part of the reactor. The stirring rod was fixed to a magnetic stirrer coupling (15) which was mounted at the top part of the SLPR. Using a coupling joint (16) the magnetic stirrer coupling was connected to a laboratory stirrer.

The cooling jacketed (liquid cooling using a cryostat) enabled reactor tempering and prevented evaporation of the reaction solution during long term operation. The modular draft tube was implemented to ensure accessibility of the reactor tube for cleaning and modifications.

Table 1: SLPR glass and peripheral components.

Nr.	Component	Manufacturer	Reference
1	DN 100 LF cover low design, without groove	DWK Life Sciences	CLFL100
2	NS 29/32 Conical ground joints	NORMAG	CNSS2942
3	GL 18 screw thread tubes	DWK Life Sciences	CGL018
4	DN 100 LF pipe section, with groove	DWK Life Sciences	CLFW100
5	DURAN® tubing draft tube Ø 46 mm	SCHOTT	D04623
6	DURAN® tubing reactor tube Ø 100 mm	SCHOTT	D10025
7	DURAN® tubing cooling jacketed Ø 150 mm	SCHOTT	D15030
8	DN 100 LF quick release fastener	DWK Life Sciences	CQ100-L
9	Silicon O-Ring	DWK Life Sciences	292254602
10	Draft tube holder	3D printed	drafttube_holder.stl
11	Stainless steel connecting rods	Custom made	connecting_rod.stl
12	600 mm Stirring Rod	Bola	C472-20
13	Stirrer draft tube	3D printed	stirrer_drafttube.stl
14	Stirrer bottom part	3D printed	stirrer_bottom.stl
15	Magnetic coupling	Bola	C520-24

1.4 Setup Components 3 L SLPR

Figure 4: Flow chart of the stirred loop photoreactor setup (right) and corresponding experimental setup (left). R-1: Stirred Loop Photoreactor, MFC-1: mass flow controller, CV-1: check valve (gas), V-1: two-way valve (liquid exhaust), M: overhead stirrer, LED-1: LED module, PS-1: power supply, HE-1: cryostat, B-1: gas scrubber, GC: gas chromatograph.

Figure 4 depicts a flow chart of the SLPR setup (left) and a picture of the physical setup (right) used for the experiments. All used setup components are listed in Table 2. Argon gas was supplied both as carrier gas for the gas chromatograph (GC) and purge gas for hydrogen detection. Therefore, the argon supply line (5 bar) is split with a T-connector into two inert gas streams (Argon in). One stream is directly connected to the carrier port of the GC, the other stream is supplied to the mass flow controller (MFC-1) to regulate the purge gas flow directed towards the SLPR. Since the SLPR operates at slight overpressure, the MFC is protected using a check valve (CV-1) to prevent liquid pushback into the argon line. The MFC is connected to the SLPR using 8 m 1/8" FEP tubing. The FEP tubing is connected to the bottom part of the SLPR using a GL 18 screw joint. The purge gas passes the reactor and is diverted at the top part of the SLPR through FEP tubing (GL 18 screw joint connection) into a gas scrubber (B-1) filled with molecular sieve to prevent liquid vapor being carried towards the sample line of the GC. B-1 is connected to the sample port of the GC for continuous hydrogen detection. A manual GL 18 2-Way Stopcock (V-1) is connected to the bottom part of the reactor as liquid exhaust to empty the SLPR after operation.

Table 2: Instrumentation and peripheral components used for 3 L SLPR experiments.

Nr.	Flowchart Reference	Component	Manufacturer	Reference
1	GC	Gas Chromatograph	Thermo Scientific	Trace 1310
2	MFC-1	Mass flow controller	Bronkhorst	F-201CV-200-RGD-11-E
3	CV-1	Check valve	Swagelok	SS-2C-1
4	-	FEP Tubing 1/8"	Bola	S1815-08
5	-	Fitting flangeless for 1/8" tubing	Fischer Scientific	12942129
6	-	HT Laboratory Screw Joints 1/8" tubing GL 18	Bola	D629-42
7	B-1	Gas scrubber	Bola	N1662-24 A
8	-	Molecular sieve 3A	Thermo Scientific	CAS: 308080-99-1
9	V-1	GL 18 2-Way Stopcock	Bola	E684-18 A
10	-	GL 18 screw cap	Bola	CS018HT
11	-	GL 18 olives bent	Bola	D582-04
12	-	LED and SLPR holder	3D printed	LED_SLPR_holder.stl
13	M	Overhead stirrer	Witeg	HS-50A

3 L SLPR LED Module

The 3 L SLPR was irradiated using four LED modules each consisting of 3 x 6 LEDs (connection: 6 LEDs in a row, 3 rows in parallel) depicted in Figure 5. LEDs were mounted on aluminum heatsinks (ATS-EXL75-300-R0, Advanced Thermal Solutions INC.) at M3 threads with a spacing of 30 mm between the LED SMDs. Each LED row was protected by a resistor limiting the LED current to 700 mA. Each LED module was operated at constant current using a laboratory power supply (Korad KA3005P).

Figure 5: 3 L SLPR LED Module and corresponding circuit diagram.

2. 3 L SLPR Mixing Time Analysis

2.1 Experimental Procedure Mixing Time Analysis

For mixing time analysis commercially available food coloring (E133) and deionized water were used. The reactor was first filled with demineralized water. The respective stirring speed was then set and maintained for several minutes until the liquid flow was considered in equilibrium. During this time, a camera was positioned so that a video of the entire reactor could be recorded. A tracer volume of 8 mL was injected from the top using a syringe. Videos were taken under red light, as the blue tracer absorbs light of this wavelength and contrasts were therefore visible best. Experiments were conducted for stirring speeds of speeds of 430, 560, 740 and 860 rpm.

2.2 Mixing Time Evaluation

Mixing time evaluation was conducted based on an adapted procedure proposed by Li et al.^[2]. The videos of the dye experiments were analyzed with a Python script (see ESI “Evaluation_RCV.ipynb”). Rectangular regions of interest were defined within the draft tube and the annular region of the SLPR, the mean red channel value for each area was calculated and saved for each frame of the video. Mixing times of the reactor within the draft tube and the annular region were evaluated frame by frame via the drop of the red-channel-value RCV after tracer injection and the stabilization time of the RCV upon complete mixing. The latter was determined by a stable RCV over a prolonged time and in close proximity to the minimum

RCV of the measurement. Figure 6 depicts the results of the stirring speed dependent mixing time analysis, indicating similar mixing times within the draft tube and annular region of the

Figure 6: Mixing time with the draft tube and annular region of the 3 L SLPR at stirring speeds of 430 rpm, 560 rpm, 740 rpm and 860 rpm (left) and picture of dye experiments and RCV regions of interest (right).

3 L SPLR.

3. Catalyst Characterization

{Mo₃}-CN_x materials prepared according to literature (batch 1)^[4] and the scaled procedure (batch 2) presented in this work were characterized with respect to surface morphology, chemical composition, and elemental distribution of the Mo₃S₁₃-PCN using a ZEISS LEO 1550 VP scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) from Ametek, USA. The SEM was operated at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV. To prepare the sample for SEM imaging, a few milligrams of the Mo₃S₁₃-PCN material were dispersed in 1.0 mL of ethanol using sonication for 10 min. Subsequently, a thin film of the sample was obtained by drop-casting a few microliters of the suspended sample onto a conductive Ti foil substrate and allowed to dry at room temperature. To improve the conductivity and achieve higher resolution SEM imaging, a 20 nm thick layer of Au was sputtered onto the sample surface. For EDS mapping, the samples were not sputtered with Au to avoid interference during the determination of Mo.

3.1 $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ SEM/EDX Characterization (Batch 2)

Figure 7: SEM images of (a,b) $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (c,d) Mo_3S_{13} -PCN photocatalyst at different magnifications.

The SEM images (Figure 7a and b) reveal that the Mo_3S_{13} phase is composed of elongated rod- and blade-like structures, extending to the micrometer scale in length and featuring relatively flat surfaces. These elongated Mo_3S_{13} particles are densely packed and intergrown, forming a loosely stacked, hierarchical assembly with significant interparticle voids. In addition to the primary rods, smaller platelet- and fragment-like $\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}^{2-}$ domains are observed decorating the surfaces and edges of the larger structures, indicating a secondary nucleation or partial exfoliation process. This morphology suggests a layered growth mechanism, characteristic of Mo_3S_{13} materials, where stacked lamellae preferentially extend along specific crystallographic directions. The resulting architecture provides a high density of exposed edges, which is beneficial for catalytic applications, as these sites are commonly associated with enhanced activity in MoS-based systems. Figure 7 c and d show the SEM images of polymeric carbon nitride after mixing with $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$, where a layered structure with a rough surface and agglomerated, irregular particles is observed. Notably, the elongated $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$

rods remain clearly distinguishable and are intimately associated with the polymeric carbon nitride particles, indicating successful incorporation of $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ within the composite.

Figure 8: SEM-EDX elemental mapping images of C, N, Ti, Mo, and S on a particle.

Figure 9: EDX spectra and elemental composition.

SEM–EDX analysis reveals a C/N-rich composition with minor Mo and S contents, yielding 43.9 at.% C, 52.1 at.% N, 1.1 at.% Mo, 2.6 at.% S, and trace Na (0.3 at.%).

EDX elemental mapping reveals the presence of a polymeric carbon nitride matrix characterized by a homogeneous distribution of carbon and nitrogen across the analyzed area. Molybdenum is detected at low overall concentration and appears as spatially localized domains embedded within this matrix rather than being uniformly dispersed, indicating that Mo is present as discrete surface-modifying species. Importantly, the Mo signal shows a clear spatial correlation with sulfur, consistent with the formation of $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ domains anchored to the carbon nitride surface. The absence of isolated Mo-rich or S-deficient regions rules out metallic or oxide Mo species and gives evidence for a configuration in which $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ is integrated as a surface modification rather than a bulk phase. Overall, the mapping demonstrates that carbon nitride serves as the dominant host phase, while $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ is present as finely dispersed, interfacially coupled domains within the carbon nitride matrix

3.2 {Mo₃}-CN_x SEM/EDX Characterization (Batch 1)

SEM–EDX analysis depicted in Figure 10 reveals a C/N-rich composition with minor Mo and S contents, yielding 45.6 at.% C, 50.9 at.% N, 1.6 at.% Mo, 1.9 at.% S. According to elemental mapping images depicted in Figure 11, similarly to the {Mo₃}-CN_x materials prepared using the scaled procedure (batch 2), Molybdenum is detected at low overall concentration and appears as spatially localized domains embedded within this matrix rather than being uniformly dispersed, indicating that Mo is present as discrete surface-modifying species. Importantly, the Mo signal shows a clear spatial correlation with sulfur, consistent with the formation of [Mo₃S₁₃]²⁻ domains anchored to the carbon nitride surface.

Figure 10: EDX spectra and elemental composition.

Figure 11: SEM-EDX elemental mapping images of C, N, Ti, Mo, and S on a particle.

3.3 Post Catalysis $\{Mo_3\}$ -CN_x SEM/EDX Characterization (Batch 1)

SEM images recorded after photocatalysis do not reveal any noticeable morphological changes compared to the pristine material, indicating that the overall structure of the MoS-modified carbon nitride is preserved during catalytic operation (Figure 15 a,b).

Furthermore, SEM–EDX analysis (Figure 15 c) indicates that the material largely retains its carbon nitride–dominated composition, with C and N remaining the major constituents, demonstrating the structural stability of the polymeric carbon nitride matrix under operating catalytic conditions. Molybdenum and sulfur are still detected at measurable levels and remain correlated, suggesting that the Mo_3S_{13} species are preserved during photocatalysis rather than being leached or transformed. The slightly reduced sulfur content relative to carbon and nitrogen may indicate partial sulfur loss or surface restructuring of $[Mo_3S_{13}]^{2-}$ under catalytic conditions, which is commonly observed for active Mo–S sites. Overall, the post-catalysis composition confirms that the catalyst maintains its MoS-modified carbon nitride architecture, supporting its durability and sustained catalytic functionality.

Figure 12: Post catalysis SEM images of (a,b) Mo_3S_{13} -PCN photocatalyst at different magnifications and (c) elemental composition.

3.4 $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ Preparation and IR Characterization

$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was synthesized according to Dave and colleagues and further used to synthesize $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ following the procedure proposed by Fedin et al.^{[5][6]}. Attenuated total Reflectance-Fourier transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was carried out on a Bruker Alpha II FTIR spectrophotometer containing a Diamond crystal ATR unit. The data was recorded with 24 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and the spectrum was background-corrected within the Bruker OPUS 8.1 program suite.

Figure 13: IR spectrum of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

4. HER Performance Comparison

Table 3: Performance comparison of photocatalytic hydrogen production using $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$.

Nr.	reactor	stirring	V_r / mL	MeOH:H ₂ O	$\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x / \mu\text{mol}$	$\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O} / \mu\text{mol}$	t / h	$\text{H}_{2,\text{total}} / \mu\text{mol}$	$r_{\text{mean}} / \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$	$\xi_{\text{ext}} / \%$	AQE / %	TON / 1	TOF / min^{-1}
1	5 mL GC vial	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3.75	3.01	0.80	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.236	5016.7	22.24
2	5 mL GC vial	500 rpm	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3.75	2.29	0.61	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.180	3816.7	16.94
3	5 mL GC vial	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3.75	0.97	0.26	$5.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.076	1616.7	7.18
4	5 mL GC vial	500 rpm	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3.75	0.71	0.19	$4.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.056	1183.3	5.25
5	5 mL GC vial ^[1]	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	6.00	9.98	1.66	$2.15 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.413	16633.0	46.20
6	5 mL GC vial ^[1]	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	6.00	16.75	2.79	$4.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.097	27920.0	77.56
7	5 mL GC vial ^[1]	yes	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	6.00	0.01	1.99	$2.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.069	19864.0	55.18
8	5 mL GC vial	600 rpm	2	1:9	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-1}$		7.00	3.00	0.43	$3.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.75 \cdot 10^{-2}$	4.6	0.026
9	Schlenk tube ^[4]	yes	10	1:9	0.12		3.00	0.48	0.16	$5.32 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.019	24.9	0.059
10	0.5 L SLPR	740 rpm	470	9:1		0.141	25.80	689.58	136.00	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-1}$	24884.3	16.08
11	0.5 L SLPR	740 rpm	480	1:9	25.20		21.53	3508.69	32.02	$6.25\text{E} \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.25\text{E} \cdot 10^{-2}$	27.4	0.02
12	0.5 L SLPR ^[2]	560 rpm	460	1:9	42.11 Pt-CN _x		69.30	2946.20	42.52	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.251	70.0	0.02
13	3 L SLPR	no	2820	9:1		0.845	37.13	4308.67	116.03	$2.43 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.024	5093.0	2.29
14	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2820	9:1		0.845	20.68	8314.50	401.99	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.112	9828.0	7.92
15	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2820	1:9		0.845	19.40	145.76	7.51	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	172.3	0.15
16	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	151.20		21.55	3045.93	141.34	0.061	0.061	20.1	0.016
17	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	106.25		27.85	3816.93	137.05	0.059	0.059	35.9	0.021
18	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	70.83		21.02	3000.48	142.77	0.061	0.061	42.4	0.034
19	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	35.42		21.02	2642.47	125.73	0.054	0.054	74.6	0.059

5. Photonic Evaluation

All commercially available reagents and solvents were purchased from companies as follows: sulfuric acid (95–97 %): Merck, sodium acetate: Sigma-Aldrich, di-potassium oxalate monohydrate: Sigma-Aldrich, 1,10-phenanthroline: Alfa Aesar, and methyl orange: VWR. Reagents were used directly without purification.

5.1 Photon Flux Calculations

To compare the photonic performance (external photonic efficiency and apparent quantum efficiency) of the used photoreactors to literature, an estimation of the externally applied photon flux (q_{ext}) and absorbed photon flux (q_{abs}) is required.

q_{ext} and q_{abs} can be calculated for narrow-banded emitters like LEDs using a monochromatic approximation according to Eq. (1). q_{ext} can be calculated for a given P_{rad} with peak emission wavelength (λ_{peak}), Planck's constant (h), the speed of light (c) and Avogadro's number (N_A).

	$q_{\text{ext/abs}} = \frac{P_{\text{rad}} \cdot \lambda_{\text{peak}}}{N_A \cdot h \cdot c}$	(1)
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5.2 Photonic Characterization Modular Photoreactor

Radiometry

Radiometric measurements were performed using two LED types (UV 365 nm, blue 455 nm) listed in Table 4. LEDs were characterized at constant electrical current ranging from 100-1000 mA in 100 mA increments. Measured optical powers were converted to photon fluxes under the assumption of monochromatic emission at the peak emission wavelengths of the respective LEDs (UV 365 nm peak emission: 365 nm^[7] and blue 455 nm peak emission: 455 nm^[8]). For the radiometric measurements LEDs were coupled to the integrating sphere using a 10 mm port. The integrating sphere was coupled to an Avantes Avaspec-ULS2048CL-EVO-RS 02/17 spectrometer (200 μm slit Slit-200-RS) using an Avantes FC-UVIR600-2-ME-SMA/FC fiber optic cable. Optical powers calculations were based on calibration data using an Energetiq EQ-99X-FC plasma light source as reference. The results of the radiometric measurements are depicted in Figure 14.

Table 4: Characterized LED and product numbers.

LED	Manufacturer	Product Number
365 nm	New Energy	LST1-01G01-UV01-00
455 nm	New Energy	LST1-01F06-RYL1-00

Figure 14: Calculated optical powers and corresponding photon fluxes for the evaluated UV 365 nm and blue 455 nm LEDs.

Chemical Actinometry

Actinometric measurements were conducted using the potassium ferrioxalate actinometer based on an adapted procedure proposed by Ziegenbalg et al.^[1,9,10]. To derive the absorption efficiency (ξ_{irr}) of a single reactor (5 mL GC vial) within the Modular Photoreactor placed in the 8-vial (circular diameter = 46.4 mm) sample holder at a vertical distance of 7 cm from the irradiation module and aligned with an additional 8-vial alignment ring fixed at a vertical position of 6 cm. Experiments were conducted using the 90x90x100 mm Modular Photoreactor corpus printed from white PLA (Raise 3D premium)^[1].

Figure 15: The experimental setup for actinometric photonic characterization of the modular photoreactor is shown on the left. The modular photoreactor is placed on a magnetic stirrer, and the LED is connected to a laboratory power supply (Korad KA3005P). The samples are positioned in an eight-vial holder inside the modular photoreactor (right).

Actinometer Preparation:

The actinometer solution was freshly prepared at the day of experimentation under red light. First, 8.8418 g of dipotassium oxalate monohydrate were weighed into a plastic weighing dish. Subsequently, 2.7852 g of iron(III) chloride were weighed out rapidly and transferred to a beaker. While stirring with a magnetic stir bar at 250–500 rpm, 50 mL of 0.05 M H₂SO₄ were added, followed by stepwise addition of the dipotassium oxalate monohydrate. Whenever a clear solution was obtained, additional dipotassium oxalate monohydrate was added and the procedure was repeated. In between, further portions of the sulfuric acid solution were added as needed. Afterwards, an additional 0.6473 g of dipotassium oxalate monohydrate was weighed and added to the beaker. Once all solids had completely dissolved, the content of the beaker was transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with solvent. The flask was stoppered and shaken thoroughly, and the solution was then transferred back into the beaker.

Developer preparation:

Subsequently, a developer solution (0.03 M sodium acetate, 0.003 M 1,10-phenanthroline) was prepared. For this purpose, 2.460 g of sodium acetate and 0.550 g of 1,10-phenanthroline were transferred into a 1 L volumetric flask. 0.05 M sulfuric acid solution was then added stepwise under gentle shaking to dissolve the solids. Afterwards, additional 0.05 M sulfuric acid was added and the flask was swirled again until a clear solution was obtained. The flask was filled to the 1 L mark with 0.05 M H₂SO₄.

Actinometric procedure:

To determine q_{abs} , reference samples (1 mL) of the actinometer solution were taken before and after experimentation to take potential actinometer conversion into account. Thereafter, 1 mL of the actinometer solution was added to 19 mL of 0.05 M H₂SO₄. 5 mL of the diluted actinometer solution were then transferred into 15 mL of developer solution and shaken again to ensure complete mixing.

8 GC vials were equipped with PTFE coated magnetic stirring bars and filled with a volume of 3 mL actinometer solution. The vials were capped using screwcaps and positioned in the modular photoreactor placed on a magnetic stirrer. Actinometric studies were conducted using the UV 365 nm LED operated at a constant current of 1000 mA and constant stirring at 500 rpm. Actinometric studies were conducted for a total of 120 s with a sampling interval of 15 s. After each irradiation cycle, 2 × 1 mL aliquots were sequentially withdrawn from one vial diluted with 19 mL portions of 0.05 M H₂SO₄. The mixture was capped and shaken, and subsequently 5 mL of this solution were transferred into 15 mL of developer solution. To ensure similar irradiation conditions for each irradiation cycle, the probed vial was then refilled with 2 mL of actinometer solution and placed at the original position within the Modular Photoreactor.

The absorbance of the developed solution was measured in a quartz cuvette ($d = 1$ cm) using a Biochrom WPA S800+ tabletop spectrometer at a wavelength of 510 nm. Absorbance raw data can be found as ESI in the file `actinometry_results_UV_365nm_LED.txt`. The evaluated absorbance data for the taken duplicates is provided as ESI in the file `absorbance_eval_UV_365nm_LED.csv`. Figure 16 (a) depicts the calculated actinometer conversion over time and (b) the corresponding calculated photon flux. A mean $q_{abs} = 210.36$ nmol \cdot s $^{-1}$ can therefore be reported for UV 365 nm operation at 1000 mA. Using the radiometrically determined $q_{ext} = 2905.5$ nmol \cdot s $^{-1}$ for UV 365 nm LED operation at the corresponding current, a $\xi_{irr} = 7.24$ % can be calculated.

Figure 16: (a) Actinometer conversion over time for LED irradiation (UV 365 nm) at 1000 mA within the modular photoreactor under constant stirring at 600 rpm and (b) calculated photon flux.

5.3 Transmission Measurements 3 L SLPR Draft Tube Holder

Transmission measurement of the polymerized resin was conducted using a 3D printed disc with a thickness of 2 mm and the radiometric setup described in section 5.2. The white (W) reference measurement was conducted with an open 30 mm port for direct irradiation with the plasma light source and the dark (D) reference measurement with a covered port. The total transmission (T_{tot}) was determined using Eq. (2) with (S_{tot}) being the raw transmission spectrum of the irradiated disc.

	$T_{total} = \frac{S_{tot} - D}{W - D}$	(2)
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Transmission measurements revealed close to no transmission for $\lambda < 400$ nm and 81 % transmission at $\lambda = 455$ nm. Figure 17 depicts T_{tot} of the sample discover a wavelength range of 300-1000 nm.

Figure 17: Transmission of 3D printed sample disc.

6. Sources

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